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The care of Environment: A moral virtue or a secular duty

An Integration Paper

Submitted to

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Abstract:

The essence of this paper is to create awareness on the impending disaster that may result from the abuse of the eco-system due to human activity. In this paper I have tried to project the topic from religious, secular and have also added a philosophical outlook according to Naess. This work used the qualitative method of research involving secondary method of data collection such as written literature, internet materials, among others.

General Introduction:

The Canticle of St. Francis has been like a mantra to me since my childhood. I was touched by his reference of the ‘brother Sun and sister Moon’. My earliest memories are of accompanying my grandpa to our fields and him telling me how the Mother Earth would provide us with food as a mother nurtures her young. This feeling of oneness with the nature only grew as I came in contact with the writings of St. Francis of Assisi. I took up Botany as my Major in my graduation, with a view that I could learn something useful to further my interest in Ecology.

As I joined the Jesuits, I came to know about the four Universal Apostolic Principles and that one of them is ‘Caring for our common home’. I taught Catechism to young children in Andheri; in one of the Jesuit parishes and one of the subjects we taught them as a part of the curriculum was Ecology! This was coupled with Pope Francis’ speech on 20th February 2020, in which he spoke about making our religious education more inclusive, with the ecological aspects.

All of this made me think **if theologizing Environment conservation would have more tangible impact on the eco-conservation scene or are our secular laws enough for the job?** A recent survey conducted by ‘Pew research’ found that 97% of the Indians believed that God exists. These people also believe in organized religion and profess one or the other faith. In this paper I will try to find out what the major religions in India (Hinduism, Islam, and Christianity) speak about Environment protection and the secular laws we have which try to do the same. I will also find out what some philosophers have said about the topic and find out the contribution of philosophy as a field of thought to the aspect of ecological conservation. I shall also try to find the impact of both (religious and secular) on the public mindset and reach a conclusion about which laws are more effective.

Chapter One: The Ecological Crisis

Damage to the environment could affect every person and every living organism in some way. The following are among the most common and most damaging causes.

1.1. Pollution:

It is the introduction of harmful substances into the environment. The most common pollutants are: Chemical wastes in the form of effluents and gases, CFC gases used in coolants, Chemical pesticides and fertilizers, etc.

1.2. Destruction of natural habitats

Flora and fauna require specific natural habitats for their survival. Humans have changed the habitats by deforestations, flooding of valleys by building dams and other ways. This has led to extinction of several species.

1.2.1. Deforestation

Large scale deforestation by humans for a variety of reasons has led to severe climate change increasing the global warming by greenhouse effect.

1.3. Use and abuse of natural resources

The rampant use of natural resources like oil, natural gas, timber and water has led to severe complications in the form of climate change and socio-economic divide.

1.4. Climate change (global warming)

Although there is no global consensus on the climate change due to human intervention, the effects include rising sea levels and more severe weather patterns.

This makes environment a very serious concern for the humanity and requires some serious intervention by the humans on global level.

Chapter Two: Major Religions on Ecology

India is the origin of four major religions, viz. Hinduism, Buddhism, Jainism and Sikhism. The Indians are basically religious minded and as per the research conducted by Pew Research 97% Indians believe in the concept of God. This is in sharp contrast to the European nations where it is less than 50%.

Religious faiths and spirituality have an incredible influence on the lives of people, and we must recognize this criteria and its power for good. The degradation of the natural world is a challenge that affects all of humanity. So we need men and women of faith, and we need spiritual and religious leaders, to mobilize action to change our apathy towards ecological crisis. We need a shared sense of inspiration, and faith, and a higher sense of goodwill for the sake of humanity and its future. Let us now see what various religions have to say about protecting ecology.

2.1. Hinduism on Ecology.

The sustenance of the environment is one of the cardinal teachings of the Hindu tradition and in this regard it points out clearly that a good environment is indispensable for a healthy life. The fundamental teachings of Hinduism point to the implications of the relationship between human beings and their environment. For example, the dharma ecology explains the mechanism for creating respect for nature and the consequences of not doing so. Hindus contemplate divinity as the one in many and many in one. The concept of 'God is one and is everywhere present' is found in Vedas. For example, Rig Veda says: 'He is the one God, producing heaven and earth, welds them together with His Veins and Wings' – 10.81.3. Hence, the Hindu religion is pantheistic in nature and believes that God resides in all things including living and non-living things. Furthermore, in Gita 13.13, the Lord Krishna says: Sarvam avritya tishthatil ("he resides everywhere").

Divinity is omnipresent and takes infinite forms, example, and many Hindus think of India's mighty rivers like the Ganga is a goddess. Hinduism expresses the firm belief that the natural environment in which people are placed is a manifestation of divine nature itself. An essential aspect of the concept of Dharma is the protection of the environment. Our environmental actions affect our Karma. The earth (Devi) is a goddess and our mother and deserves our devotion and protection. Ahimsa (nonviolence) is the greatest Dharma. Ahimsa to the earth, hurting or harming another being damages one's Karma and obstructs advancement toward Moksha (liberation).

The Hindu religion, unlike the biblical account of creation, points to the fact that mankind has no dominion over the environment, although, he can make judicious use of it. In accordance to this teaching, we can hold that: Man is the trustee of the universe and he is authorized to use natural resources, but has no divine power of control and dominion over nature and its elements. Hence, from the perspective of the Hindu culture, abuse and exploitation of nature for immediate gain is unjust and irreligious.

The Hindu tradition, teaches that God exists in all living things, including simple microscopic organisms and other living things like the plants. This belief has its origin from the concept of reincarnation. Hindu teachings have it that the human soul can reincarnate in any form, like in the form of lesser and simple living organisms or in the complex form and by implication the need to treat all forms and categories of life with respect and reverence. All living beings are sacred because they are parts of God and should be treated with respect and compassion. This is because the soul can be reincarnated into any form of life. Most Hindus are vegetarian because of this belief in the sanctity of life. Even trees, rivers and mountains are believed to have souls and should be honored and cared for.

2.1.1. Conclusion

Hinduism is made up of different philosophical, ritualistic, theistic and atheistic traditions. By extension, it consists of multidimensional views toward nature. From their concept of dharma and karma, the Hindu tradition teaches that proper management of nature and its elements bring good rewards and happiness and that mismanaging them, especially by altering the ecosystem, attracts bad reward and unhappiness. This is how karma can affect us and our future generations; hence human beings are encouraged to live in harmony with the nature.

2.2. Buddhism on Ecology:

Environmental change was not a pressing subject at the time of the Buddha so he did not give teachings specifically on this subject. He did recognize that local communities could be affected by the behavior of his followers and so, for example, he set rules that monks and nuns should never relieve themselves in or near running water, i.e. where people would want to wash or drink. Similarly, he also ruled that monks and nuns should not disrupt the established habitat of any other creature, nor kill other living creatures, for example when building new quarters. Some forms of Buddhism teach the idea of the inter-relatedness of everything. This means that humans depend on nature and nature depends on humans in a symbiotic relationship. Therefore, if people learn to live simply and in harmony with the world, the whole of the environment will benefit.

2.2.1. Noble Eightfold Path

Eight guidelines were taught by the Buddha to help humans escape suffering and approach enlightenment. These include 'right mindfulness'. If humans are 'mindful' of the effects of their actions on the world, then this is an effective way to avoid causing damage to nature and other living creatures.

2.2.2. Five Precepts

These are guidelines about how to act properly. One of these precepts has a direct bearing on a Buddhist attitude to the environment. Buddhists should abstain from taking life, and this includes

any form of life. This is linked to the idea of rebirth that can include the possibility of being reborn as an animal. Rather than taking life, Buddhists are encouraged to show compassion to all creatures and believe that all life-forms are special, not just human beings. This first Precept relates to the concept of ahimsa. This is based on the idea of causing no harm.

2.2.3. Karma

If a person has a right mindset, Buddhists believe that the actions they perform will be beneficial not just to themselves but to the whole world, including the environment. They believe that our actions affect the planet in a harmful way because we are selfish and we crave things. These actions will only result in more suffering in the future. The effects of karma will continue to work in a person's rebirth, so by being compassionate, we will improve our own future and that of the environment. The Buddhist declaration at Assisi stresses the need for all people to have respect for wildlife and for the environment. The main threat to the world so far has been that human beings have been indifferent to the effects of their actions on other creatures.

2.3. Jainism on Ecology

Jainism has often been described as ecological religion or religious ecology. The three principles of Jainism, namely *Ahimsa*, *Aparigraha* and *Anekantvada* echo the teachings of non-violence, non attachment and non possession. The three basic Jainism concepts can play a key role in establishing ecological balance.

2.3.1. Non-violence

The basic teaching of Mahavir is Ahimsa. Ahimsa is the supreme tenet. Jainism stands out from other religions in its application of non violence. It has been observed today by the great persons that with reference to ecology the choice is no longer between non violence and violence, but, it is between non-violence and non-existence. This is indicative of the gravity of situation today. In the wider sense non –violence implies ‘Right to life for all’ coming from ‘Respect for life’. Thus it is ethically oriented principle of conduct which can promote the spirit of universal brotherhood and peaceful coexistence not just for humans but for all creation. In *Achanranga Sutra* it has been said, ‘every human being wants to live, nobody likes suffering. Therefore do not inflict suffering on anybody. This is non-violence.’ Non-violence is the crux of wisdom and is the basic virtue. Nature is treated reverentially in Jainism. It asks us to shape our actions with a more care for their environmental consequences. In Jainism, non-violence is not merely a ritual but discipline for all at all times. It provides us with environmental ethics and would help humanity to live in harmony with nature. Jainism teaches not to exploit nature in our greed for wealth and power. If we practice non-violence and be a little cautious perhaps, we can prevent disturbing ecology. Non-violence implies

restricted consumption of natural resources. In social context it implies practices of restraint in all activities. No extravagance or waste should be there due to neglect and carelessness. Lord Mahavira rightly observed that non-violence is wholesome for all living beings. Positively, it implies the universal friendliness. It is abundantly clear that non-violent lifestyle is imperative to save mankind.

2.3.2. Aparigraha: In Jainism, the principle of Aparigraha calls for non-attachment, or non-possessiveness. Attachment is considered an obstacle to spiritual liberation because the excessive pursuit of material possessions leads to the desire to own such objects. Thus, it implies that we are the caretakers of the environment, and not the owners. Hence we should remain detached from it and care for it as would a caretaker. For this reason, Jain dharma recommends that people should extinguish or minimize desires to only what is necessary and strive to limit one's needs.

2.3.3. Anekāntavāda meaning "non-absolutism," is one of the basic principles of Jainism that encourages acceptance of relativism and pluralism. According to this doctrine, truth and reality are perceived differently from different points of view, and no single point of view is the complete truth. It thus, motivates people to search for and accept different perspectives on the conservation of ecology by using alternative sources of energy and prevent the destruction of ecosystem.

2.4. Islam on Ecology

The ethical base of Islam which is derived from the imperatives laid down in the Qur'an and expressed in the practice of the Prophet, comes under numerous headings. They can however be distilled into just three precepts for our purposes, bearing in mind public good to be the ultimate objective. They are to do what is right, forbid what is wrong and act with moderation at all times: "Let there be a community among you who call to the good, and enjoin the right and forbid the wrong. They are the ones who have success" (Q 3:104). The Qur'an uses an environmental theme in exhorting humankind to be moderate, "it is He who produces gardens, both cultivated and wild, and palm trees and crops of diverse kinds and olives and pomegranates both similar and dissimilar. Eat of their fruits when they bear fruit and pay their dues on the day of their harvest, and do not be profligate. He (Allah) does not love the extravagant" (Q 6: 142). The Quran refers to creation or the natural world as the signs (ayat) of Allah, the Creator, and this is also the name given to the verses contained in the Qur'an. Ayat means signs, symbols or proofs of the divine. As the Qur'an is proof of Allah so likewise is His creation. The Qur'anic view holds that everything on the earth was created for humankind. It was God's gift (ni'mah) to us, but a gift with conditions nevertheless.

It is important for Muslims to both engage in the debate concerning the environmental crisis and at the same time work in partnership with the other traditions and like-minded groups and

organisations from outside the world of Islam. At the root of the crisis is personal behaviour and if Muslims were true to themselves their spontaneous inclination would be to prioritise the welfare of others with whom they share a finite planet, which needs to be cared for in the interests of the generations to come. Islamic environmentalism begins with the self and then radiates to the home, the school, the mosque and the wider community and out to all humankind. There are endless possibilities for Muslim activism in the common struggle to save the planet once ecological issues are seen in the light of giving service in a world created for us by an act of divine love. Much progress can be made if both Muslim countries, and individual Muslims themselves, take the environmental heritage of their faith more seriously.

Many Muslims believe human beings have guardianship or khilafah of the planet, which means that each individual should act as a guardian or khalifah. They will be held accountable for their guardianship on the Day of Judgement. Humans should treat the world with respect, as it is not ours to abuse. Guardianship allows humans to make use of the environment for their survival, but this must never be taken to the level of exploitation.

One of the central pillars of Islam is Tawhid. This concept of oneness is reflected in Allah's creation. Muslims believe that Allah has given reason to humans. Humans must use this gift in their stewardship of creation: Human beings are stewards or guardians (khulafa' – the plural of khalifah in Arabic) and they will have to give an account of how they carried out their guardianship of the environment on the Day of Judgement. Muslims may understand and apply these principles to the question of looking after the environment in a variety of ways:

- Muslims are allowed to make use of what nature provides but they must avoid waste and excess.
- Shari'ah law protects animals from cruelty, defends forests and limits urbanisation.

Muslim leaders, representing all the major groups of Muslims, drew up a Seven Year Plan in 2009. The aim was to improve the environment. Actions include limiting the use of new resources, encouraging recycling, and developing guidance for business on how best to protect the environment from exploitation. By helping people to focus on God and not on distorted values linked with money and possessions, Muslims hope to re-establish harmony in the world between people and with nature. Sunni Muslims have created haram zones where people have to respect natural resources and not exploit anything that is there. They have also created animal reserves to protect wildlife and forests. These actions aim to re-establish nature as Allah wants it to be.

2.5. Sikhism on Ecology:

2.5.1. Personal Responsibility: Basically Sikhism believes that it is impossible for us to save the environment, until we recognize that we as individuals are responsible for our actions. The Sikh Holy Scripture, the Shri Guru Granth Sahib Ji states, "*we shall reap the results, of the seeds which we sow*".

Example, if we unsustainably remove trees from the planet, then we are sowing the seeds of our own destruction. Sikhism also encourages humanity to follow the principle: 'benefit the whole human race'. This is very much a holistic view which states that we as custodians of planet Earth must perform those deeds which benefit everyone or at least the greatest number of people. However, in order for this to work, we need to become less selfish. The Sikh Gurus taught people to be completely selfless by example. Without selfless, responsible, and 'good for all' orientated individuals, communities, and governments, any environment improving initiative will be ineffective.

2.5.2. Respect mother Earth: Sikhism encourages people to respect and live in harmony with the environment, including animals and plants. The Sikh Holy Scripture (SGGSJ) states, "*Air is the Guru, water is the father and Earth is the great mother. Day and night are like two nurses who look after us*". Respect for Mother Earth starts with the little things at an individual level, such as disposing of litter in bins. It is not acceptable for a Sikh to dispose of litter in the street. At a national and international level, respect for the Earth implies the sustainable use of the planet's resources and the responsible use of human technologies such as nuclear energy and weapons.

2.5.3. Respect for All Creatures: The Sikh Gurus were great lovers of animals. Indeed, Guru Gobind Singhji is sometimes known as 'the one with the falcon'. There are many references in the Guru Granth Sahib Ji that refer to the whole of creation as being sacred, because God's spirit permeates through all of it. The SGGSJ states, "*In all beings is the Lord pervasive, the Lord pervades all forms male and female*" (Guru Granth Sahib Ji, p.605). Sikhs are commanded to respect all forms of life, including animals and plants.

2.5.4. Managing the Earth: Guru Gobind Singh Ji said, "*Recognise the human race as one unit*". This means that political, national, racial, religious, and economic divides are all meaningless. Sikh philosophy would require all developed nations to help the people of developing nations, to ensure they enjoy the same quality of life as everyone else. Unfortunately, this philosophy is still theoretical. The human race still does not behave as one unit. One reason for this is that the countries of the world lack the mechanism by which effective communication and co-operation can occur. The desire of the Sikh Gurus was the establishment of a society called the Khalsa (pure ones), that would protect the human rights and freedom of every human being. This same philosophy applied to the modern world would involve the creation of a world government (the Khalsa), which would manage and safeguard the interests of humanity by ensuring proper management of the planet's resources. It would be responsible for ensuring that the actions of the human race are those which benefit everyone. However, a world assembly (the Khalsa), with a foundation based on selflessness, humility, and responsibility may help to halt and even reverse the destruction of our planet. It is important to

remember that the word, 'Khalsa' does not solely refer to baptized Sikhs. It refers to those individuals who are pure by heart and who share the same philosophy. This includes all religious, racial, and cultural groups.

2.6. Christianity on Ecology:

Christians believe that the Earth belongs to God and that humans are stewards in charge of its care. Most Christians believe that God gave human beings a special responsibility within creation to cultivate it, guard it and use it wisely. This is called stewardship. Man has to work within creation and to look after it: God took the man and put him in the Garden of Eden to work it and take care of it (Genesis 2:15). Humans are given everything for their needs, implying that they can use whatever they want from creation for their survival: Everything that lives and moves about will be food for you. Just as I gave you the green plants, I now give you everything (Genesis 9:3). However, as the Earth belongs to God, humans must respect it and hand it back to God unspoiled: The earth is the Lord's, and everything in it, the world, and all who live in it (Psalm 24:1). These passages from the Bible show the dominant message is that God is the one who provides for humans and humans should show they are thankful by taking care of what God has given them. The Christian Declaration on Nature drawn up at Assisi in 1986 makes the following points very clearly: All creation, both with and without humans, has a close interdependence which was made in this way by God. This harmony of creation is to the glory of God. Humans have the role of protecting all created things, not abusing or destroying them. All types of exploitation of the world and its resources and all creatures are rejected. Humans must not do anything that risks damage to the world. For many Christians, the guiding principles are to respect God's handiwork of creation, not to exploit any aspect of creation and to be aware of the needs of future generations. Many Christians apply these principles to the question of looking after the environment in a variety of ways.

The Roman Catholic Church has responded to the challenges raised by environmental issues by stressing the need for every individual and every nation to play their part. The important points that the Church makes include the beliefs that:

- i. The creation has value because it reveals something about God the creator.
- ii. Creation has value in itself.
- iii. Humanity depends on God but everyone has a responsibility for the world and the environment.

Pope John Paul II said, 'the dominion granted to man by the Creator is not an absolute power, nor can one speak of a freedom to 'use and misuse', or to dispose of things as one pleases'. (Evangelium Vitae, Section 42 (1995))

The Church of England has made many statements about environmental issues. The Anglican Communion Environmental Network has made the following statement on the environment: Christianity is first and foremost a concern for the whole of the created order — biodiversity and

business; politics and pollution; rivers, religion and rainforests. If Christians believe in Jesus they must recognise that concern for climate change is not an optional extra but a core matter of faith. The Evangelical churches are very aware of how much environmental issues are linked to human poverty: We recognise that poverty forces people to degrade creation in order to survive; therefore we support the development of just, free economies which empower the poor and create abundance without diminishing creation's bounty. Evangelical Declaration on the Care of Creation 1994: This principle could apply to the issue of deforestation, especially when it is carried out by poor people who are trying to grow enough food for their families.

The Quakers are very conscious of humanity's effects on the Earth. They encourage their members to make changes in their lives which enable them to live simply and minimise their exploitation of the Earth: Where we see crisis, we also see opportunity to remake society as a communion of people living sustainably as part of the natural world. By leading the simpler lives of a low-carbon society, we draw nearer to the abundance of peace, freedom and true community.

2.7. Judaism on ecology:

Stewardship: Jews believe that God created the world (Genesis) and gave human beings a special responsibility within creation to cultivate it, guard it and use it wisely. This is known as stewardship. God gives man control of the environment. Some people interpret this to mean human beings have been given total power over everything on Earth to do as they want, but most Jews believe that humans should act responsibly, ensuring the environment is not treated badly. Man has to work within creation and look after it: The Lord God took the man and put him in the Garden of Eden to work it and take care of it (Genesis 2:15). The Tanakh makes it clear that, as the whole Earth belongs to God and so humans have to respect it and hand it back to God unspoiled. The earth is the Lord's, and everything in it, the world, and all who live in it (Psalm 24:1). These passages can be used to support different sides of the argument about how Jews should care for the environment. However, the main message is that God is the one who provides for humans and humans show they are thankful by taking care of what God has given them.

Tikkun Olam Tikkun Olam means 'repairing the world' and expresses the Jewish desire to encourage harmony in the world. This refers to social harmony, people being able to live in peace with each other, enjoying health, justice and prosperity. It also refers to a duty to take care of the environment. One of the ways Jews try to heal the world is the sabbatical year. According to the Bible, every seven years, the land should be allowed to lie fallow, so that the natural ingredients in the soil can be replenished and better harvests can be expected in the future.

The Jewish Declaration on Nature at Assisi in 1986 makes the following important points:

- i. God made order out of chaos when he created the world.
- ii. Man accepted responsibility before God for all of creation, at the beginning of time.

- iii. The righteous Jew lives in the world and respects the rights of other people and creation itself
- iv. Humans were given dominion over nature, but God commanded them to behave towards the rest of creation with justice and compassion.

For most Jews, the guiding principles on the environment are to respect God's creation and the role that God has given humans to play. Many Jews believe that to love God means to love all his creatures. By treating nature well, human beings can regain the original state of harmony with all of creation, like the state described in the Garden of Eden. Many Jews understand and apply these principles to the question of looking after the environment in a variety of ways: Jews should not destroy anything that can be of benefit to humans. This includes animals, plants and natural resources. Even in times of warfare, trees should not be damaged. Jews must honestly accept the difficulties that face them in restoring the damaged environment. This must not become fear because fear will prevent people taking the necessary actions. Jews need to change their lifestyles in big and small ways, as individuals, as a group and as a state.

An example of this is the commitment by the state of Israel to cut its carbon emissions by 20% by 2020. Jewish communities must ensure the sabbatical years are effectively observed. 2015 was a global sabbatical year. Jews should only use energy that comes from renewable sources, as far as possible. Liberal Jews are more progressive in their attitude to the environment. They are willing to cooperate with all groups striving to improve the state of the world.

Chapter Three: Secular laws in India

The Environmental laws in India give huge importance to maintain an ecological balance of environment by safeguarding the forests and wildlife of the country. These can be said to be among the best in the world in terms of their encompassing a range of ecological threats, particular to our nation. In this segment I shall bring out the secular laws which are in force in our nation.

3.1. Constitutional provision of Environmental Law

There are certain constitutional provisions which give certain power and rights to the citizens to protect environment. Let's have a look:

3.1.1. Article 48A: This Article comes under the Directive principle of the State policy. This article implies that State shall endeavor to protect the environment. It also emphasizes on safeguarding the forests and wildlife of the country. Article 48A imposes a duty on State to protect the environment from pollution by adopting various measures.

3.1.2. Article 51A (g): The Article 51 A(g) states that it shall be the duty of each and every citizen of India to protect and improve the natural environment that includes lakes, rivers, forests and wildlife. This Article also focuses on showing compassion for living creatures. This article is similar to Article 48A, but the only difference is that it concentrates on fundamental duty of citizens whereas Article 48A instructs the state to perform their duties and protect environment. Hence, it is our duty to not only protect the environment from pollution but also improve its quality.

3.1.3. Article 253: This Article gives power to Parliament to create laws for the country in order to implement any treaty conventions and agreement with other countries. By this article, Parliament enacted various laws in order to protect environment like - Water Act 1974, Air Act 1981 and the Environmental Protection Act 1984.

3.1.4. Article 246: The Article 246 divides the subjects of legislation between Union and State. It also provides the details of Concurrent list in which both the Union and State make laws by sharing the jurisdiction comprising the protection of mines, wildlife and minerals development. So, both State and Union have power to enact laws to protect the environment. Article 246 also provides the extra power to Parliament in order to make laws in State list for the National interest.

3.1.5. Article 32 & 226: This article provides right to citizen to approach to Supreme or High Court whenever there is violation of fundamental right by PIL (Public Interest Litigation). This article helps preserve the environment and maintain ecological balance. This Article also dictates that environment conservation is not just the duty of government but also the responsibility of citizens of India.

3.2. Environmental Laws in India after Independence (1947)

The Indian Constitution adopted in 1950 never dealt with the subject of environment or prevention until the passing of the 1976 amendment. The post independent Indian approach was centered on the economic development and poverty alleviation.

Let's look at some of the progressive steps in context of environmental laws in India after independence:

- It was the Stockholm Declaration of 1972 that turned the attention of the Indian Government towards the perspective of environmental protection.
- Set up in 1972, the National Council for Environmental Policy and Planning was later evolved into Ministry of Environment and Forests (MoEF) in 1985.
- The Wildlife Protection Act 1972 aims at rational and modern wildlife management.
- The Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974 provides the establishment of pollution control boards both at Centre and States in order to act as watchdogs for preventing and controlling pollution.
- The Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act 1981, aims at checking air pollution via pollution control boards.
- The Forest (Conservation) Act 1980, aims at checking deforestation and diversion of forest land.
- The Biological Diversity Act 2002 safeguards the threatened species, prevents bio - piracy and water scarcity. It also regularizes the usage of natural resources and avoid its over exhaustion
- The Environment Protection Act 1986, the environmental legislation in India provides a single focus in the country in order to protect environment and aims at plugging the loopholes in the existing legislation.

3.3. Most important legislations for Environment Protection

3.3.1. The National Green Tribunal Act, 2010

The National Green Tribunal Act 2010 provides the effective and expeditious disposal of cases related to conservation of forests, environmental protection and enforcement of any legal right relating to the environment. The Act also gives proper compensation and relief for damages to persons and property, and connected matters. The Act contains proper clauses on the jurisdiction, powers and proceedings of the tribunal and penalties of contravention.

3.3.2. The Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981

The Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981 is a law passed by the Parliament of India in order to prevent and control the harmful effects of air pollution in India. The Government had passed this Act in 1981 in order to clean up the air by controlling pollution level. According to the Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981, power plants, vehicles and industries are not allowed to release particular matter, lead, carbon monoxide or other toxic substances beyond a prescribed level.

3.3.3. The Environment Protection Law, 1986

The Environment (Protection) Act, 1986 is one of the **environmental law acts** that provides the protection and improvement of the environment. Here, the term 'Environment' includes components like air, water and land and also the relationship between them including human beings, microorganisms and plants. The Environment Protection Act, 1986 had enacted this law at the United Nations Conference in order to protect the human environment.

3.3.4. The Hazardous Waste Management Regulations

Hazardous waste means any waste which can cause danger to health or environment due to its physical, chemical, reactive, toxic, explosive or corrosive characteristics. There are several legislations that directly or indirectly deal with hazardous waste management as discussed below:

- **Hazardous Wastes (Management, Handling and Trans-boundary) Rules, 2008:** It guides about the manufacture, storage and import of hazardous chemicals for managing hazardous wastes.
- **Biochemical Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 1988:** These rules were formulated for proper disposal, segregation and transport of infectious wastes.

- **Municipal Solid Wastes (Management and Handling) Rules, 2000:** It aims at enabling municipalities to dispose-off municipal solid waste in a scientific manner.

Conclusion:

India has an impressive number of environmental regulations. In 2019, 387 districts in India were contaminated by Nitrate, thereby being the prime contaminant source. As per Niti Aayog, overall, 70 percent of the freshwater sources in the country were found to be contaminated and India ranks 120 out of 122 countries in terms of water quality (statista.com). Similarly, in 2019, air pollution was responsible for around 1.67 million deaths in India. This number is equivalent to 17.8% of the total deaths in the country. Out of those, 0.98 million deaths are attributable to ambient particulate pollution, while household pollution caused 0.61 million deaths. Going by the figures, there has been a 64.2% decline in the death rate due to household air pollution between the years 1990 and 2019. India has been instrumental in taking state- and national-level initiatives to ameliorate household air pollution. The Indian government launched Unnat Chulha Abhiyan in June 2014, Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana in May 2016, and National Infrastructure Pipeline Project that has contributed to this decline (aqi.in). Yet public opinion on the effectiveness of these regulations has not always been positive. There are countless newspaper articles or reports detailing the ineffectiveness of these regulations, as well as accusations of the mismanagement of funds earmarked for these purposes, ranging from underuse and incorrect reporting to diversion of funds. Also, why were the same successes not seen in the water pollution arena? More specifically, would water pollution have been worse if the regulations had not been adopted? I studied the effect of the National River Conservation Plan (NRCP), which is the cornerstone of water pollution regulation in India. I failed to find any tangible data on statistics regarding the effect from the program.

As we all are responsible for damaging the environment, hence it is really important that we follow environmental laws and also spread environmental awareness with others. We should not let our future generations suffer from our own bad deeds. Other than following **environmental laws and policies**, we must also look forward to contribute our bit towards nature conservation like - planting more trees, making less usage of cars etc.

Chapter Four: Philosophy and Ecology

In this segment we shall have a look at the contribution of philosophers to the conservation of ecology. I have chosen a well known eco-philosopher Arne Naess, and we shall now review his ideas on the subject of ecology.

4.1. Arne Dekke Eide Naess (27 January 1912 – 12 January 2009)

Arne Naess was a Norwegian philosopher who coined the term "deep ecology". He is an important intellectual and inspirational figure within the environmental movement of the late twentieth century, and a prolific writer on many other philosophical issues. Naess combined his ecological vision with Gandhian non-violence and on several occasions participated in direct action. Deep ecology, environmental philosophy and social movement are based in the belief that humans must radically change their relationship to nature from one that values nature solely for its usefulness to human beings to one that recognizes that nature has an inherent value. Sometimes called an "ecosophy," deep ecology offers a definition of the self that differs from traditional notions and is a social movement that sometimes has religious and mystical undertones. The phrase originated in 1972 with Norwegian philosopher Arne Naess, who, along with American environmentalist George Sessions, developed a platform of eight organizing principles for the deep ecology social movement. Deep ecology distinguishes itself from other types of environmentalism by making broader and more basic philosophical claims about metaphysics, epistemology, and social justice.

Naess stated that while western environmental groups of the early post-war period had raised public awareness of the environmental issues of the time, they had largely failed to have insight into and address what he argued were the underlying cultural and philosophical background to these problems. Naess believed that the environmental crisis of the twentieth century had arisen due to certain unspoken philosophical presuppositions and attitudes within modern western developed societies which remained unacknowledged. Naess believes that we are in the midst of a grave and gathering catastrophe born of foolhardy production and consumption habits, resulting in an inequitable distribution of material wealth. Social justice, in this context, cannot be enough, for rectification by proliferation rather than by renunciation can only lead to environmental crisis and finally to collapse. Faced with such fallout, disaffected with a scientific method that proceeds in and for itself, and discontent with a pursuit of a wealth that self-propagates for its own sake, Naess looks instead to tread wisely and lightly. "Simple in means, and rich in ends," he says while speaking for quality of life over and against standard of living, and celebrating the virtues of smallness and slowness in an age of scale and speed.

Naess has always had a talent for contextual thinking, and among the many intellectual stages he has cycled through, the philosopher and the ecologist gradually fused to forge the persona of eco-philosopher, or ecosopher for short. While the distinction between philosopher and 'ecosopher' might

seem a difference of degree, it is actually a difference of kind: whereas the philosopher loves wisdom in the abstract and for its own sake, the ecosopher values wisdom that has a particular household valence, in both the personal and the planetary senses. For Naess, the transition from philosopher to ‘ecosopher’ came via a methodology he termed empirical semantics, an intervention in the field of linguistics whereby he endeavoured to study language not in an absolute sense, but strictly in particular contexts. This move, away from an epistemology predicated on the odd pairing of nominalism and universalism, and toward an ontology predicated on the equally odd pairing of realism and relativism, presaged the shift from analytic philosophy to eco-philosophy. The transition itself was wholly logical, for just as each word needed situating, so too did each speaker. Naess’s own individual version of ecosophy springs from a very particular context. Known as Ecosophy-T, and described at length in *Økologi*, the T stands for Tvergastein, the arctic mountain hut Naess commissioned while still in his twenties, and where he has dwelt seasonally for almost seventy years.

4.1.1. What I like about Naess:

Here is one of Naess’s greatest gifts to thought, for while there is plenty of Naess, there is no Næssicism. Yes, there is deep ecology, and yes, there is Ecosophy T, but beyond them lie a host of other ecosophies awaiting elucidation. Call each of them Ecosophy X, for the moment, and fill in the blank at your own bidding, bringing to bear the concerns that seem to you most relevant. Tarry not, though—for you tarry not only at your own peril, but also at our collective peril. As Naess explains, and as I second, “we are not all in the same boat, but in several different boats, all of them charting a course for catastrophe.”

4.1.2. What I think is an irony of Naess:

Though Naess has spoken proscriptively about deep ecology, he has been more sparing in his categorical pronouncements about ecosophy. Of these few categorical maxims, the most notable may be that “the ideology of ownership has no place in an ecosophy.” How disappointing, then, to register chagrin at what should be a cause for celebration: the recent publication of a ten volume set titled *The Selected Works of Arne Naess* (Dordrecht: Springer, 2005). Covering a wide variety of Naess’s published and unpublished works, from early manuscripts to articles first appearing in his venerated journal *Inquiry* to scattered essays of much more recent provenance, *SWAN* (as it is labelled for short) runs to 3650 pages and retails at the shocking sticker price of ₹72,155.00! This is with a discount of 59%, thus the actual cost of these books (Vol.1-10) is ₹1,77,999.00! This is out of reach for most of academicians wanting to read his books. It is also ironical that a man who advocated ‘simplicity’ should have agreed for such an exorbitant price for his publication.

According to Peter Madsen, some critics of deep ecology claim that the movement is based on mysticism and that it appears to be more of a religion than a rational approach to environmental matters. Those critics point to the creation of the Church of Deep Ecology in Minnesota in 1991 as an

example of how the movement had devolved into a spiritual and mystical approach to nature rather than a way to solve environmental problems. Eco-feminists and social ecologists, groups having a great deal in common with deep ecologists, also found fault with the social movement. Some practitioners of ecofeminism and social ecology accused deep ecologists of having an inauthentic and superficial spirituality and not valuing issues of gender, class, and race highly enough.

General Conclusion

Environment is a multi-dimensional and multi-faced problem. It is complex and compound in nature. There are no single or simple solutions to the environmental problems. It requires a lot of persuasion, hard-work and mutual respect, and understanding. Partisan and parochial approach may hurt the cause itself. Think globally and act locally is very apt in case of Environment protection. The threat of war anywhere is danger to peace everywhere. The same is true of the Environment. The global warming, deforestation, depletion of fossil fuels, pollution and other climatic changes, remind us of the stark reality that the earth is one. Around the world, environmental regulation is one of the key public services that governments provide to their citizens. While these regulations impose costs on businesses and households by requiring them to dispose of pollution in a responsible way, in return they promise better health, a cleaner environment and other related benefits.

While these stories and reports provide insight into the functioning and challenges of implementing effective environmental regulation in India and elsewhere, what has been missing is systematic evidence on whether the regulations have succeeded in their intended purpose: to reduce air and water pollution. Moreover, these stories don't provide any insight into how the overall benefits of the regulations (in terms of pollution reductions and lives saved) compare to the costs of these systems. For example, even if one policy brings about a large improvement in people's health, the cost may be so great that the money could have been better spent on other health interventions that lead to even larger effects.

As seen from the religious point of view, all the major religions in India, viz. Hinduism, Sikhism, Buddhism, Jainism, Christianity portray man as a steward of the God's creation. This means that humans are supposed to treat the nature with utmost diligence as a servant treats things belonging to his master. This has great implication if we consider that 97% Indians believe in the concept of God and religion. Thus, secular Environmental laws if combined with religious obligations will be more efficacious and easy to enforce. Similarly, the ecosophical studies if promoted right from the school will be highly beneficial in creating awareness about ecology among the future population and its introduction and promotion as academic field will help in uniting and motivating intellectuals and ecologically conscientious people to contribute to the protection of ecology. Conservation ethics, a field of philosophy also revolves around **making human communities and ecosystems better, protecting important resources for the present and future**. This philosophical approach values the human/nonhuman dynamic in nature, recognizing how humans and the environment have an ongoing causal relationship with one another.

The religious audiences may be able to identify with ethical or moral values of environmental conservation and development, their own faith is often their primary concern (e.g. Tomalin 2002). Furthermore, religious groups might place high value on maintaining a separate cultural identity. When planning activities with faith groups, it is essential to recognize this and to respect social and

cultural boundaries in order to initiate effective partnerships. However, it might be important to encourage religious groups to create opportunities for dialogue across faiths and with secular organizations so as to dissolve the social and cultural boundaries. There is an urgent need for the formation of a secular body that helps the major religions of India to develop their own environmental programs, based on their own core teachings. This organization could also create opportunities for predominant religious faiths around the country to promote environmental conservation and sustainable development, and, occasionally, to encounter one another in mutual respect to address common ecological issues. Effective action for helping conservation and development in most cases seems to demand changes in attitudes and behaviours from religious adherents and secular organizations alike. Such changes can be brought about by highlighting success stories where adherents are shown examples of people of their own faith engaging in conservation and development activities (e.g. Kula 2001). This way of encouraging participation is often effective because members of the same faith group share the strongest cultural associations with each other. Similarly, there is need for empathy and an open mind towards faith groups on the part of conservation and development volunteers, professionals, NGOs, and donors. This simply means that secular bodies like governmental ministries, NGO's, and religious organisations should work together for environmental conservation and regeneration efforts.

The way forward

I conclude that environmental regulations in India can be successful at reducing pollution concentrations but only when regulators are sufficiently empowered and motivated. Also despite my suggestion of combining religion with secular laws and philosophy, it should be acknowledged that there is no direct causal effect of faith on conservation and development, or at least one that has yet been demonstrated by social scientists. Nor is there concrete evidence that individuals or organizations affiliated with religions are more likely to be concerned about the environment than those who are not. It is possible that faith groups are simply embracing ideas and practices that are popular or generally accepted in society. On the other hand, the ethical or moral values related to conservation and development may at least sometimes play a role in the faith groups' choice of ideas and practices. These examples thus suggest that, over time, dramatic public action may emerge, at least in part, due to religious values and from the world's predominant religious faith traditions.

Hence, I conclude that a balance of Secular laws and Religious obligation is a two pronged approach which will give us the maximum benefit by covering up the secular loopholes and also mellow down over-zealous religious enforcement.

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